

QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION AND COMPARISON OF TERAHERTZ AND ULTRASONIC TESTING OF GLASS-FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials are essential in aerospace and automotive structures, yet their safety-critical use demands reliable nondestructive testing (NDT). Ultrasonic inspection is well suited for carbon-fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRP) but struggles with glass-fiber composites (GFRP) and structural foams because scattering and attenuation mask defect echoes. Terahertz testing, which uses electromagnetic waves between 0.1 and 1 THz and needs no coupling medium, overcomes these limits for non-conductive materials. Ultrasound and terahertz are therefore complementary. This paper evaluates the best choice depending on frequency, defect size and depth.

This study quantitatively compares signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) delivered by focused ultrasonic transducers (1, 2.25, 5 MHz) and continuous-wave terahertz probes (100, 150, 300 GHz). Two specimens were prepared: a 50 mm pultruded GFRP block with blind holes 2.5 - 8 mm at nine depths, and a 15 mm expanded-polypropylene foam slab with 2-12 mm holes at two depths. Water-coupled pulse-echo C-scans and matching terahertz scans were recorded with 300 μ m steps. The signal-to-noise ratio was defined as the maximum defect amplitude divided by the maximum surrounding echo.

Ultrasonic testing detected most GFRP defects to 35 mm with the 2.25 MHz probe. 5 MHz resolved 2 mm holes but only to a depth of 15 mm, while 1 MHz penetrated the full block yet with blurred indications at higher depths. Terahertz produced higher SNR overall. 100 GHz was optimal for GFRP, imaging an 8 mm hole at 40 mm, whereas 300 GHz yielded the clearest foam images. The foam could not be inspected ultrasonically.

The signal-to-noise ratio increases with flaw size and drops with depth and frequency. Its optimum shifts deeper as frequency falls. Terahertz is besides the more expensive computer tomography the only effective method for closed-cell foams. For GFRP, 2.25 MHz ultrasound remains the most versatile for defects larger than 6 mm for ultrasonic testing, while terahertz offers superior signal-to-noise ratios. Combining both techniques maximizes defect detectability for non-carbon composite components.

1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Composite materials are gaining increasing importance in the aerospace and automotive industries due to their advantages in weight, stiffness and strength. Because of high safety requirements in the use of these materials in primary and secondary aircraft structures, composite materials demand sophisticated nondestructive testing methods, such as ultrasonic inspection, radiography or thermography. Ultrasonic testing in particular provides excellent results for the detection of a broad variety of defects and has proven to be a reliable inspection tool in recent years and is used to inspect primary and secondary aircraft structures made of carbon fiber reinforced plastics [1, 2]. However, the range of materials has expanded considerably in recent years, meaning that glass fiber-reinforced composites and foams must also be tested non-destructively. Ultrasonic testing is very problematic with these materials due to the high scattering and attenuation.

Instead, terahertz testing can be used. It is a comparatively new NDT method that works very similarly to ultrasonic testing. Instead of mechanical sound waves, electromagnetic waves in a frequency range of 0.1 to 1 THz are used for testing. The advantage of terahertz testing is that no coupling medium needs to be used. A major

disadvantage for general use is the exclusion of testing electrically conductive materials such as metals or carbon fiber-reinforced plastics. Terahertz technology is therefore particularly suitable for testing nonconductive materials such as foams or glass fiber-reinforced plastics [2]. Both materials are difficult to test with ultrasound. However, both materials are used for demanding parts for aerospace and maritime applications (Fig. 1 & 2).

Figure 1: Sailplane made out of GFRP [3]

Figure 2: Foam based radome of a German corvette [4]

Thus, terahertz testing should not be seen as a competitive process, but rather as a powerful complement to ultrasound testing [5]. Of course, there are materials, such as GFRP, where both methods can be used. In this case, it is interesting to know which method produces the higher signal-to-noise ratio during detection depending on the test frequency, defect size and defect depth, if this is possible at all. An early comparison was done by J. Dong, et.al. in terms of a qualitative evaluation [6]. The investigation presented here focusses on a quantitative comparison of the measured signal-to-noise ratios in order to obtain the optimal test method and testing frequency.

2 EQUIPMENT AND TEST PIECES

2.1 ULTRASONIC FACILITY

The research and development described was conducted at the Institut für Kunststofftechnik Westpfalz (IKW) located on the campus of the University of Applied Sciences Kaiserslautern. The institute's state-of-the-art ultrasonic system was manufactured by the company Hillger in Germany and operates in a frequency range from 0.1 up to 30 MHz in a fully digitized way (Fig. 3). Ultrasound can be applied water- and air-coupled. However, in this study only water coupling was used. The Hilgus-software package allows the realization of through-transmission tests and A-, B-, C-, D-, and F-scans, which e.g. allows the evaluation of frequency shift based on real-time Fast-Fourier-Transformation (FFT). In addition, full-waveform-scans can be performed allowing post-scanning gate-settings. In total, besides a trigger gate two evaluation gates can be set. Three scanning systems can be connected to the ultrasonic control unit:

- Four axes system for shell-like parts (40 x 60 x 80 cm) and short rotational parts
- Two axes system for rotational parts (length 120 cm, diameter 15 cm)
- Two axes system for through-transmission air-coupled ultrasonic testing.

in-house construction of the Fraunhofer-Institut für Techno- und Wirtschaftsmathematik (ITWM) with which tests for the generation of A-, B- and C-scans in the frequency range

from 70 GHz to 500 GHz

Figure 3: Ultrasonic scanner with immersion tank

Three focused transducers from Olympus NDT - Panametrics with center frequencies of 5 MHz, 2.25 MHz and 1 MHz were used for the ultrasonic tests (Fig. 4, Table 1).

Figure 4: 1 MHz, 2.25 MHz, and 5 MHz transducer

Transducer name	Frequency f [MHz]	Diameter of active element D [inch]	Focal length F [mm]	Near field length N [mm]	Bundle diameter b [mm]
V394	1	1.125	96.5	137	5.25
V304	2.25	1	76.2	244	2.07
V309	5	0.5	50.8	136	1.24

Table 1: Transducer properties

2.2 TERAHERTZ FACILITY

The terahertz test facility is an in-house construction of the Fraunhofer-Institut für Techno- und Wirtschaftsmathematik (ITWM) with which tests for the generation of A-, B- and C-scans in the frequency range

from 70 GHz to 500 GHz are possible (Fig. 5). The depth information is generated by the FMCW principle. Three probes with 100 GHz, 150 GHz and 300 GHz were used for the measurements undertaken (Fig. 6).

Figure 5: Terahertz facility

Figure 6: Terahertz probe

2.3 SAMPLES

Two test pieces were used. The first one was a pultruded glass fiber reinforced block (GFRP-block) with a thickness of 50 mm in which blind holes with diameters of 2.5 mm, 4 mm, 6 mm and 8 mm were drilled at nine different depths (5 mm, 10 mm, 15 mm, 20 mm, 25 mm, 30 mm, 35 mm, 40 mm, and 45 mm as shown in Fig. 7a. The speed of sound of this GFRP was determined to be 2.350 m/s. The second sample was an EP-foam panel (density 170 kg/m³) with a thickness of 15 mm and blind holes (diameter 2 mm, 3 mm, 4 mm, 5 mm, 6 mm, 7 mm, 8 mm, 9 mm, 10 mm and 12mm) and depths of 2.5 and 5 mm in two different depths (2.5 mm and 5 mm) as depicted in Fig. 7b.

Figure 7: Samples, a) GFRP-sample, b) EP-foam sample

3 EXPERIMENTAL

Ultrasonic testing of the GFRP-sample was done in pulse-echo with gates with a width of 4 μ m starting at 2 μ m behind the front surface echo and one gate set around the back surface echo resulting in ten C-scans for each transducer. The measurements were performed from the rear side of the sample. Because only four gates can be evaluated during one test, three measurement runs were required. The use of an auxiliary reflector did not work due to the thickness of the part and the associated attenuation of the ultrasound. The focal points were placed into

that depth were the gates were set. The C-scans were quantitatively evaluated with a custom-made program named Oculus.

The same approach was used for the foam sample but with gate lengths set around the expected defect echoes. The increment was chosen in both scanning directions to 300 μm . The foam part clamped to a stainless steel plate to avoid floating.

The terahertz tests of the GFRP-sample were performed accordingly to the ultrasonic C-scans with the focal point set in the area of interest. The foam part was inspected by means of an auxiliary reflector (steel plate) which was placed 10 mm below the rear sides of the samples. Also here, the increment was chosen in both scanning directions to 300 μm . All A-scans were stored as a full-waveform scan. Similar to the ultrasonic C-scans, the THz-C-scans of the GFRP-sample were quantitatively evaluated with features programmed into the scanning program.

4 RESULTS

It turned out that with ultrasonic testing, it was not possible to detect any defects in the foam sample. Exemplary C-scans of the GFRP-sample are shown for the blind hole defects in a depth of 15 mm (Figure 8). With the 2.25 MHz probe, most defects could be detected up to a depth of 35 mm. With the 5 MHz probe, only defects up to a depth of 15 mm could be detected. After that, the attenuation of the material was too great due to the scattering of the glass fibers. Interestingly, it was even possible to generate a backwall echo with the 1 MHz probe. However, with this probe it was only possible to image defects up to a depth of 20 mm.

Fig. 8: C-scans of the GFRP-samples with gate set between 10 and 14 μm , a) 5 MHz, b) 2.25 MHz, c) 1 MHz

The high-lying defects (5 mm depth) could not be detected in any case because the spurs from the front surface echo covered the defect echoes. The signal-to-noise ratio decreased with increasing depth and decreasing defect size. Due to the shorter wavelength of the 5 MHz transducer in comparison to the 2.25 MHz transducer (470 μm to 0,97 μm) the 2 mm defects could be found. Furthermore, it can be noticed that the 1 MHz transducer enlarges the defects significantly.

The results of the terahertz-measurements are exemplarily shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. It turned out that the 300 GHz probe was not suitable to inspect the GFRP-sample. In turn, it showed the best results for the thinner foam sample.

Fig. 9: THz-C-scan of the GFRP-samples with 100 GHz and a depth of 15 mm

Fig. 10: THz-C-scan of the GFRP-samples with 300 GHz and a depth of 15 mm

5 EVALUATION

5.1 FUNDAMENTALS

The signal/noise ratio determines how much the echo amplitude of an indication differs from that of the flawless vicinity. In order to quantify the signal/noise ratio of an indication, four different approaches can be realized:

- maximum indication amplitude versus maximum ambient echo
- maximum indication amplitude versus average ambient echo
- average indication amplitude versus maximum ambient echo
- average indication amplitude versus average ambient echo,

where the ambient can be understood as that part of the sample not including any defects. Here, the maximum indication amplitude versus maximum ambient echo in the vicinity of the defect was used for the analysis of the

signal/noise ratio. This procedure is also consistent with the optical assessment strategy of an UT-operator to identify an indication by looking at the highest difference between indication and ambient echo amplitudes (sharpest contrast). Parameters significantly influencing the signal/noise ratio are as follows:

- depths of defect
- defect size
- transducer frequency (UT and THz)
- focal length
- bundle diameter (focal point diameter)
- active element diameter
- inspection strategy (kind of echo, position of focal point)

Focal length, focal point diameter, active element diameter and frequency are transducer properties and cannot be chosen freely [1]. The influence of the remaining four parameters was analyzed by keeping two of them constant and considering the effect of variations of the two others on the signal/noise ratio.

5.2 INFLUENCE OF DEFECT SIZE

First, the dependency of the defect size was evaluated for two different depths (10 and 25 mm). The result of this evaluation can be seen in Fig. 11 and 12.

Fig. 11: Dependency of the defect size on the signal/noise-ratio (depth 10 mm)

The evaluation of the signal-to-noise ratios for the various defect sizes at a defect depth of 10 mm shows that all defects are easily detectable (Fig. 11). With ultrasound, the signal-to-noise ratios decrease with the frequency and increase with the flaw size. This is also the case with terahertz testing. Terahertz testing enables the detection of defects with a higher signal-to-noise ratio.

The result is very similar for the defects at a depth of 25 mm (half the sample thickness). The signal-to-noise ratios for ultrasonic testing are higher than for a defect depth of 10 mm, which can be explained by the surface echo that has been completely attenuated at this depth reducing the ambient noise. The signal-to-noise ratio of the 100 GHz terahertz test is again the highest. At a depth of 40 mm, only the 8 mm defect could be visualized at 2.25 MHz with ultrasound and with the 100 GHz terahertz probe with signal-to-noise ratios of just above two digits.

Fig. 12: Dependency of the defect size on the signal/noise-ratio (depth 25 mm)

5.3 INFLUENCE OF DEFECT DEPTH

First, the dependency of the defect depth was evaluated for a defect diameter of 8 because this defect is sufficiently large to be detected in all cases. The result of this evaluation can be seen in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13: Dependency of the defect depth on the signal/noise-ratio (8 mm defect)

Figure 13 clearly shows that there is an optimum for each test frequency and method. As the test frequency decreases, this optimum signal-to-noise ratio shifts towards greater defect depths. It has to be pointed out once

again that it was possible to penetrate the part under inspection with the 1 MHz probe. However, due to the focus point widening, the fault indications merged into one another, so that the indications were not evaluated.

5.4 EVALUATION OF THE FOAM SAMPLE

The evaluation of the foam sample shows a difference for the depth of the errors in this auxiliary reflector measurement. The double passing of the walls of the defect perpendicular to the beam path caused a significant attenuation of the defect in the deeper defects. This resulted in a greater signal-to-noise ratio of up to 10 dB in the defect display itself for defect sizes above 5 mm. The small defects located higher up (depth 2.5 mm) were only found with a low signal-to-noise ratio of 3 - 4 dB.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The signal/noise ratio is significantly influenced by seven parameters, which are not independent of each other. Thus, it seems to be difficult to choose the optimal transducer providing the highest detectability of defects possible whereas the defects have certain size for a given material situation. However, the minimum defect size to be detected in Airbus CFRP-aircraft components is about 6 mm in diameter according to AITM-standards. This study dealt also with smaller defects to show the limits of certain test frequencies and yielded that the 2.25 MHz ultrasonic transducer provides the highest signal/noise ratio for ultrasonic testing deeper positioned defects as depicted in Fig. 13.

The evaluation of the foam sample shows a difference for higher defects are better found with the 5 MHz probe. A very good alternative here is terahertz testing, which has a much greater selectivity of defects and defect-free areas. In addition, terahertz testing is the only NDT method besides the more expensive computer tomography with which foams can be tested in a meaningful way.

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